

Effectiveness of the Digital TVET Framework in Learning and Development through the Cascaded CPSC-Labtech ToTs on Virtual Learning

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Abstract: Digital technology integration in technical and vocational education and training (TVET) has gained momentum, especially in response to the growing demands of Industry 4.0. This study looks at the Digital TVET Framework's ability to improve learning and development outcomes through the Cascaded CPSC-Labtech Training of Trainers (ToTs) on Virtual Learning. The framework is designed to adapt traditional TVET methodologies to digital environments. It uses virtual learning platforms to provide scalable, competency-based training. The Cascaded ToTs model was implemented in stages. This study examines how this method affects trainers' ability to use digital pedagogies and learners' acquisition of vital skills. The research uses a mixed-method approach that integrates quantitative metrics such as completion rates, skill assessments, and learner satisfaction, along with qualitative data from focus groups and interviews with participants. The results show a significant improvement in trainers' ability to deliver digital content, and a corresponding increase in students' participation and skill mastery. The findings highlight the potential of the Digital TVET Framework as a sustainable model for capacity building in the digital era. These findings have implications for a wider adoption of the Digital TVET Framework across the globe.

Keywords: *Digital TVET Framework, Training of Trainers, Virtual Learning, Learning Management System*

INTRODUCTION

Blended learning has become the standard in educational systems since the onset of the 'new normal' within the post-pandemic environment. With most, if not all institutions forced to migrate through digital learning (both asynchronous and online setups), the landscape through which 21st century teaching and learning methods have evolved, creating new opportunities and challenges for both teachers and learners alike. First, educators from all competency levels experienced a rethinking of roles and functionality, with which traditional tools for teaching have become irrelevant and less useful in gauging the ability of the learners to gain knowledge. Second, digital learning (remote teaching) has changed the perspective of how educational institutions see learners from just active receivers of information to self-organizing individuals and autonomous social agents who are able to learn without direct [physical] supervision from teachers [from pedagogy to heutagogy] (Rapanta, et al. 2021). Moreover, an analysis of various

systematic 21st century education [IR 4.0] frameworks have become less and less adaptive to the exponentially increasing requirements associated with the technology in today's time (Gonzales-Perez, et al. 2022). These changes have allowed the need to incorporate the use of artificial intelligence (AI), and virtual and augmented reality to teaching and learning systems, adding another dimension in today's digital learning environment.

This migration proved to be challenging especially to the Technical Vocational Education and Training (TVET) sector. This is because technical sectors in TVET e.g. automotive, electrical, and HVAC (heating, ventilation, and air conditioning) systems are taught more in practice through workshops, simulations, and laboratory work to TVET learners rather than in classrooms using traditional (face-to-face) setups despite incorporation of vestiges of 21st century skills competency-based curricula in TVET institutions. To cope with this challenge, this paper aims to examine the overall effectiveness of the digital TVET framework, as espoused within the design of the CPSC-Labtech virtual training programs, in the development of pedagogical tools in digital learning and development through a quantitative survey that measured TVET trainers' perceptions towards the effectiveness of their methodologies on their students using key parameters such as student accessibility, feedback, performance, and peer-assessment. In addition, gaps toward the effective implementation of these pedagogical tools as a result of the employment of the digital TVET framework in CPSC member countries are also explored.

CPSC-Labtech Digital TVET Framework: ToTs on Virtual Learning

As one of the international intergovernmental training providers in Asia Pacific with 16 active member governments, CPSC constantly engages at the forefront of providing relevant and up to date capacity building programs to its TVET stakeholders. Together with Labtech, one of the largest TVET education systems designers and manufacturers of courseware for TVET programs, the organization focuses to provide comprehensive 21st century skills-infused technical and engineering learning solutions for TVET institutions, polytechnics, and universities all across the globe. Through CPSC, Labtech has facilitated online training programs on the following fields: (a) automotive technology; (b) air conditioning and refrigeration systems (HVAC); (c) electrical basics; and (d) renewable energy systems. The partnership between CPSC and Labtech has since implemented a total of 24 online programs from August 2021 to March 2024.

Generally, the training program runs for four days- with lectures, sessions, and individual workshops (asynchronous and synchronous) being facilitated by the instructors. All programs are done online, through Zoom and CPSC-Labtech Academy's virtual LMS. Much of the topic revolves around the discussion on the digital TVET framework and its benefits, in particular, the educational aims of virtual learning. The aim of which is to produce heightened awareness among TVET learners on the use of interactive, self-determined learning in TVET centers. This move towards heutagogy from the traditional pedagogical and andragogical learning mechanisms would allow a learner-centered learning environment through the use of virtual TVET systems.

Fig. 1: Digital and Virtual TVET Framework
 Source: Labtech International, Ltd.

The training programs mainly facilitate workshops and give participants the opportunity to use the virtual LMS provided by Labtech first-hand. This LMS, through the CPSC-Labtech Academy (<https://cpscnew.labtech-academy.com>), offers virtual training as AR simulations through 3D gaming technology, to teach the fundamentals of the mentioned sectors. Table 1 below enumerates the sub-topics per course sector in the LMS. When starting a new topic, the user is first given a pre-test, to assess their prior knowledge on the sub-topic. After which, the user proceeds to the primary study materials which include a module on background theory, fundamental concepts, and interactive learning through the simulations. The focus of the LMS is to allow the user to use the interactive learning module, which incorporates the VR models according to the module topic. At the end of each topic, a post-test is conducted to gauge the overall effectiveness of the simulations.

Table 1. Sub-topics of the Virtual Modules in CPSC-Labtech LMS

Automotive Technology	HVAC	Electrical System	Renewable Energy System
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Basic Engine Fundamentals Automotive Electrical and Electronic Systems Petrol Fuel Systems Diesel Fuel Systems Automotive Air Conditioning and Heating Systems Engine Management Systems Manual Transmissions Automatic Transmissions and Transaxles Wheel Drive Systems Propeller Shafts and Differential Brakes Systems Steering and Suspension Systems Hybrid Vehicles Battery Electric Vehicles (BEV's) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> HVAC Fundamentals Electric Circuit and Controls Electric Motors Refrigeration and Air Conditioning Compressors Refrigeration System Components Refrigeration Systems Air Conditioning Systems Automotive Air Conditioning 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Electrical Fundamentals Electrical Instruments/Panel Meters Electrical Components Electrical Machines Wiring and Installation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Renewable Energy (Solar-radiation energy, solar street lighting, wind energy, wind turbine system, solar thermal system, etc.)

OBJECTIVE AND SCOPE

The overall objective of this research study is to assess the extent through which the CPSC-Labtech training programs assisted TVET trainers from the CPSC member countries implement digital learning in their own respective institutions using the digital TVET framework. The proponents of this study generally assume that the assessment is critical to understanding the prospect of continuously developing capacity building programs such as the CPSC-Labtech virtual training, to bridge the gap between the requirements of the 21st century skills and preparing TVET learners to adapt as digitally-skilled individuals.

This research paper presents a scenario where virtual TVET training in practical sectors such as those in automotive technology, HVAC, electrical basics, and renewable energy systems are employed by TVET instructors as part of their pedagogical instruments in teaching and learning delivery. In this sense, training of trainers is considered as a necessary program for virtual learning to be cascaded down to TVET learners. This study is limited however, to the exposition of the CPSC-Labtech virtual programs in measuring the extent to which digital learning outcomes are used by TVET trainers across Asia Pacific as a pedagogical tool. Any other virtual TVET programs conducted by other training providers are not presented in this paper.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Embracing Digital Learning in TVET

The emerging developments in the field of information and communication technology (ICT) have created a new era of the teaching and learning environment through the use of digital learning, which have been growing rapidly in recent years and are expected to continue in the future. TVET institutions need to develop high-quality digital learning content that is engaging, interactive, and accessible. Apart from an interactive digital learning environment, learning materials should foster and promote collaborative learning among students through discussion, group projects, and virtual classrooms (Tissenbaum and Slotta, 2019). Moreover, TVET institutions must provide appropriate training for teachers and instructors in using new-age digital tools and technologies such as haptic technology, virtual, augmented, and mixed realities to deliver effective learning experiences and transfer knowledge and skills to their students to be future-ready for the world of work.

IR 4.0 in educational systems in TVET has ushered in an array of innovative teaching methods that leverage technology's potential to foster engagement, customization, and collaboration in education and training systems. These methods not only address the challenges of today's rapidly changing world, but also equip students with 21st century skills and mindset to thrive in the future. This would require TVET graduates to easily find employment in relevant fields and industries and thrive in the world market. A recent study (Nurjanah, I. and Ana, A., 2021) assessed the factors that affect TVET graduates' readiness in the world of IR 4.0. The ability factor, which includes learning achievement, level of intelligence, practical experience, discipline, and expectancy to enter the world of work, plays the most dominant role in TVET graduates' readiness for work. Moreover, the same study laid out that there is a general lack of

efforts coming from governments to improve work readiness of TVET graduates, a global market characterized by low wages, low skills and low productivity work and limited career opportunities are unattractive to graduates, while curricula practice less attention to practice-based courses as well as soft skills. Even trainers are not adequately prepared to face the great demands due to technological developments, industrialization, and the ramifications of digital learning migration.

Digital transformation leads to massive changes in the skill sets needed for work and life. Effective use of digital technologies is also a key factor in meeting the Sustainable Development Goals. Teaching and learning need to address the new trends and challenges brought about by the introduction of ICT in almost all areas. However, instructors in many TVET institutions are only equipped to teach using traditional methods, including lectures, discussions, case studies, programmed instructions, role play, demonstrations, experiments, and educational field trips, among others. There is found to have a lack of training available for TVET instructors to upskill themselves to develop innovative teaching methods and instruction materials required for digital learning, especially in practical courses. These methods transcend traditional classroom boundaries, aiming to engage and empower students in new and exciting ways. Flipped classrooms, for instance, have shifted the learning paradigm by encouraging students to absorb instructional content independently at home, freeing up class time for collaborative activities and discussions. (Singh, et al., 2018) Blended learning seamlessly combines in-person instruction with digital resources, offering a customized learning experience that caters to individual paces and preferences.

According to Zulnaidi, K. and Majid, M. (2020, p. 38), this gap is directly influenced by TVET lecturers' readiness for IR 4.0 which is then measured according to the amount of sufficient courses and training programs relating to IR 4.0 attended by lecturers. Implementation of suitable programs such as round table conferences, online training, and simulation-based activities are pathways towards building capacity of TVET instructors to gain the skills demanded by IR 4.0 education. Their research also found that a high level of TVET lecturers' readiness towards IR 4.0 can directly impact IR 4.0 implementation as a way for teaching and learning, whereby commitment is an important factor to assess how TVET lecturers understand concepts under IR 4.0. This exposure of TVET lecturers would have them gain 21st-century skills especially in nine areas namely: digital literature, decision making, project management, creative/analytical thinking, problem solving, entrepreneurship and techno entrepreneurship, global thinking, and life-long learning.

Indeed, it is imperative for TVET trainers to continuously train and retrain their professional skills in order to imbibe a learner-centered approach in classroom and outside-classroom management. According to a study conducted to review the structure and performance of TVET teachers in Malaysia (Mohamad, et al., 2005), teacher training in TVET can be defined as the main role in providing the skill to fulfill the school level TVET needs. A major part of this teacher training is the capacity of TVE trainers to have certain level of competence in facilitating blended learning (the paper enumerates several examples including online learning, teleconferencing, the Internet, computer-assisted learning (CAL), and web-based distance learning (WBDL) - with the disclaimer that the term during the time of publication is still ill-defined). Blended learning has now become a common feature not just in TVET, but in every educational system around

the world due to the forced migration brought about by the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The research study employed a quantitative analysis of the extent through which the digital TVET framework, as learned by the TVET trainers who participated during the CPSC- Labtech programs have cascaded to the TVET learners through the employment of similar teaching pedagogies. The study will measure the effect of incorporating digital learning outcomes through four parameters: (1) student access to digital learning materials; (2) student feedback; (3) student performance; and (4) student peer-review. To assess this, a survey tool has been circulated to the TVET trainers who successfully completed the training programs provided by CPSC and Labtech from 2021 to 2024. The parameters were measured according to their perception as their learners use the digital teaching materials in their practical classes. Figure 2 shows the relationship between the independent and dependent variable in this research as well as the moderating variables.

Participants

The data from this study was collected through purposive sampling. The sample population are the TVET trainers from various TVET institutions across Asia Pacific who have attended the online training programs of CPSC and Labtech. A total of 458 TVET trainers, instructors, lecturers, and facilitators across CPSC member countries from Bangladesh, Bhutan, Fiji, India, Malaysia, Maldives, Myanmar, Nepal, the Philippines, Sri Lanka, and Thailand are identified from 2021 to 2024 (March). The breakdown of the sample population per country and per program sector can be seen in Table 2 below.

Table 2: Breakdown of Sample Population per Country and Course Attended

Distribution of Sample Population Per Country and Course Attended						
Country	Automotive Technology	HVAC	Renewable Energy	Electrical Basics	TOTAL (per country)	RESPONSES OBTAINED
Bangladesh	1	3	2	26	32	6
Bhutan	20	17	0	1	38	5
Fiji	19	1	0	1	21	4
India	23	2	0	2	27	19
Malaysia	28	2	38	2	70	10
Maldives	1	0	1	0	2	2
Myanmar	25	20	30	1	76	12
Nepal	0	0	1	11	12	9
Pakistan	16	1	0	20	37	10
Philippines	25	1	19	3	48	14
Sri Lanka	2	19	19	14	54	9
Thailand	2	35	2	2	41	1
TOTAL (per sector)	162	101	112	83	458	
RESPONSES OBTAINED	31	5	30	35		101

Moreover, the table above also shows the breakdown of obtained responses from the post-program survey questionnaire circulated to the respondents from April to May 2024. From the sample population of 458, a total of 101 respondents have submitted a response to the survey circulated from 12 countries (22.05% response rate). The variance of responses obtained from the countries and sectors attended is evenly distributed except for Thailand, who only had one response; and the HVAC sector with only five respondents obtained.

Parameters

The research study employed an online survey instrument to quantify the indicative parameters used to examine the relationship between the identified variables. Primarily, the survey instrument looked into the overall extent through which trainers who attended the CPSC-Labtech programs develop and use the digital TVET framework taught to them as part of their pedagogy in the classroom. In particular the questions asked on the development and use of digital learning materials (such as but not limited to the use of LMS tools, game design softwares, interactive digital tools and applications, moodle boards, online classrooms, etc.) by the selected trainers, and the extent through which the development of these learning materials are supported by the institution financially and infrastructure-wise.

Further, the extent of digital learning by the selected trainers are ultimately determined by four sets of parameters: (1) Student Access, (2) Student Feedback, (3) Student Performance, and (4) Student Peer-Review. This shows that the extent of digital learning employed by the trainers are examined reflective of the student learning outcomes in the curricula and overall reception of the trainers' students in response to digital learning. Lastly, these set of parameters are further cross-examined with the sector through the fields the trainers were trained in: (a) Automotive Technology, (b) Electrical Basics, (c) Air Conditioning and Refrigeration (HVAC), and (d) Renewable Energy Systems.

Table 3. Dependent Variables and indicative sub parameters in the study

Parameters (Dependent Variables)	Indicative Sub Parameters Examined
Student Access	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access of learners to digital learning materials employed by their trainers using multiple devices • Efficiency, convenience, and understandability of the employed digital learning materials • Use of digital learning materials outside school hours (for asynchronous sessions)
Student Feedback	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Positive reception of learners towards the employed digital learning materials • Students preference to digital learning over traditional modes of learning • Learners can operate the use the digital learning materials with minimal supervision
Student Performance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase in learners' competency in the areas being taught with digital learning • Adaptive learners to the demands of digital learning mechanisms employed • Learners' enthusiasm to learn through digital means
Student Peer-Review	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learners' perceptions on the accuracy of the information in digital learning materials • Learners' perceptions on the sustainability and long-term use of digital learning

Measurement Indicators

Using a five-point Likert Scale, the parameters were measured using the agreement of the respondents to statements that are indicative of the sub parameters enumerated in the previous table. Table 4 shows the range of normal distribution for the employed ordinal scale (1-strongly disagree, 2-disagree, 3-neutral/somewhat agree, 4-agree, and 5-strongly agree). The normal distribution range was taken from the common statistical derivatives in employing Likert scales as a research tool to assess human perception and attitudes towards qualitative statements (Likert, 1932).

Table 4. Scoring range of the likert scale used in the study

	Value	Normal Distribution Range
Strongly Disagree	1	1.00-1.80
Disagree	2	1.81-2.60
Neutral/Somewhat Agree	3	2.61-3.40
Agree	4	3.41-4.20
Strongly Agree	5	4.21-5.00

To further calibrate the parameters used in the survey, the authors determined the Cronbach Alpha Coefficient α (Konting et al., 2009) from the variance values obtained from the respondents per variable. The first five questions on the development of digital learning materials based on the 100 respondents produced a coefficient of α **0.834** while the next 11 questions on measuring the effectiveness of these digital learning materials to student learning

and development produced a coefficient of α 0.947. The produced coefficients in this study attest to the overall reliability index of the questionnaire and the parameters through which the objectives of this study were observed.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Country and Sector Analysis

From the 100 responses obtained, a total of 12 CPSC member countries were represented namely, Bangladesh, Bhutan, Fiji, India, Malaysia, Maldives, Myanmar, Nepal, Pakistan, Philippines, Sri Lanka, and Thailand. The country analysis allows the authors of this study to differentiate the status of digital learning per country participation during the conducted CPSC-Labtech programs. It can be noted in Table 5 that the distribution range of all parameters per country responses relatively falls between 3.26 to 4.44 for the independent variable, and between 3.20 to 4.75 for the dependent variable. Upon analysis, it can be assumed that while the Digital TVET Framework is casually employed by TVET instructors in all countries, the extent of its use through the continuous development of digital learning materials and outcomes still vary per country albeit most respondents agreed that digital learning materials are continuously developed and utilized in the classroom, and that there is a generally positive effects on the attended CPSC-Labtech training programs to the utilization of these developed digital learning materials in the classroom. Trainers from Bangladesh, Bhutan, Myanmar, Nepal, and Sri Lanka responded lower to the independent variable parameter compared to trainers from other countries. This can be attributed to the following: (i) adequacy of financial and infrastructure support to digital learning; (ii) adequacy of facilities for in-house use of digital learning materials; and (iii) stability of network connection to suit digital learning modalities. These three sub parameters under the independent variable are precedent to the viability of the targeted TVET trainers to continuously develop digital learning materials under the digital TVET framework.

Table 5 Average distribution range of country respondents to survey parameters on employment of digital learning to TVET classes

Parameters	BLD	BHU	FIJ	IND	MYS	MDV	MYR	NPL	PAK	PHL	SLK	THA
Independent Variable <i>EXTENT OF USE OF DIGITAL TVET FRAMEWORK</i>												
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Development and use of digital learning outcomes and materials by TVET trainers 	3.43	3.40	4.30	4.25	4.44	4.20	3.66	3.26	4.30	4.44	3.91	4.40
Dependent Variable <i>RECEPTION OF TVET LEARNERS TO EMPLOYED DIGITAL TVET FRAMEWORK</i>												
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Student Access Student Feedback Student Performance Peer Assessment 	3.22 3.78 3.94 3.83	3.20 3.73 3.33 3.70	4.25 4.17 4.17 4.50	4.49 4.33 4.33 4.41	4.53 4.43 4.50 4.70	3.33 4.00 4.17 4.75	4.10 4.03 4.07 4.20	3.48 3.86 3.81 3.71	4.46 4.46 4.67 4.63	4.41 4.19 4.22 4.22	4.19 3.90 4.24 4.29	3.67 4.67 4.67 4.50

The distribution range above accounts for the reception of TVET learners to the employed digital TVET framework by their trainers. It shows that there is a direct link between the identified variables. The distribution range for student access, student feedback, student performance, and peer assessment are generally lower for country respondents whose development of digital learning materials using the digital TVET framework are made difficult for trainers due to lack of ICT infrastructure and financial support given by the TVET institutions. On the other hand, the distribution range also shows that there is indeed a general positive student reception to the digital learning modalities employed by trainers from countries such as Fiji, India, Malaysia, Maldives, Pakistan, Philippines, and Thailand. This warrants that the use of digital TVET framework in employing digital learning among the students is generally effective in countries where TVET institutions provide ICT infrastructure and financial support towards digital learning.

Further, Table 6 shows the average distribution range of all respondents per sector attended in the implemented CPSC- Labtech programs. This breakdown assesses if there are moderators to the correlation between the study's independent and dependent variables, i.e. if the sectors (automotive technology, electrical basics, renewable energy, and air conditioning and refrigeration) to which the respondents attended affected the analyzed reception of TVET learners to the development and utilization of the employed digital learning materials using the digital TVET framework. It can be noted that the identified moderating variables did not produce significant distinction between the independent and dependent variables. The distribution range of the responses from each attended sector are within the normal range indicative of this study.

Table 6 Average distribution range of respondents per sector attended in the CPSC-Labtech programs

Parameters	AT	EB	RW	HVAC
<u>Independent Variable</u> EXTENT OF USE OF DIGITAL TVET FRAMEWORK <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Development and use of digital learning outcomes and materials by TVET trainers 	4.09	3.92	4.04	3.63
<u>Dependent Variable</u> RECEPTION OF TVET LEARNERS TO EMPLOYED DIGITAL TVET FRAMEWORK <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Student Access Student Feedback Student Performance Peer Assessment 	4.19 4.06 4.08 4.36	4.03 4.10 4.21 4.10	4.24 4.12 4.23 4.28	3.39 3.89 4.06 4.08

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the research study provided an overall picture of the relationship between the development of employment of the digital TVET framework from the cascaded CPSC-Labtech programs by the participating TVET trainers to student learning and development in the participating member countries of CPSC. The analysis shows that employing digital learning outcomes has a positive impact on the overall student learning and development in terms of four parameters: i. student access, ii. student feedback, iii. student performance, and iv. peer assessment.

However, while a positive correlation between the variables was established in the findings, the analysis also showed that for some countries where institutional support for ICT (infrastructure and financial) are lacking, student learning and development through the digital TVET framework are not as effective as it did for country respondents with sufficient infrastructure and financial support to the employment of digital learning modalities.

Moreover, setting aside the above mentioned factor on institutional support for digital learning delivery, variance on the distribution range on factors in relation to student access and student feedback can also be seen. This can be reflective of two things; (a) students' geographical location hinders them from accessing the employed digital learning materials outside of their technical centers; and (b) students' still prefer traditional modes of learning than digital learning. While the purpose of this study is just to observe the normalcy of the distribution ranges between the identified variables, a more in-depth study can be made to focus solely on student perception in regard to digital learning.

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